

THE EFFORTS OF 'PENDIDIKAN AGAMA ISLAM' TEACHERS IN CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC AT SMPIT NURUL FIKRI TULUNGAGUNG

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Abstract : *During the Covid-19 pandemic, the Government through the Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan (Minister of Education and Culture) instructed all educational institutions to carry out distance learning. The purpose of this study was to determine the efforts of the Islamic Pendidikan Agama Islam teacher in implementing distance learning. The method approach used is qualitative. The results of field research indicate that Islamic Religious Education teachers have difficulty implementing learning, because educational institutions are not ready to support the distance learning process. Learning is done through a social media software application, because it is easy to use and all parents of students must have it. The teacher conveys the learning content then students respond by sending the results of assignments based on Student Worksheets via social media.*

Keywords: *Classroom Management, Covid-19 and pandemic*

Introduction

Recently, various countries in the world are being shocked by the outbreak of a disease caused by a virus called corona or better known as covid-19 (Corona Virus Diseases-19). This virus initially began to develop in Wuhan, China. The virus outbreak is indeed very fast, spreading to various countries in the world. So that the World Health Organization (WHO), declared the outbreak of the Covid-19

virus as a world pandemic today. Positive Covid-19 patients in Indonesia until Monday (13/7/2020) are still growing, namely 76,181 positive people, 36,689 recovered, 3,656 died. Positive confirmation of Covid-19 reached 76,181 people, 36,689 recovered, and 3,656 people died, spread across 34 provinces and 461 districts / cities.¹

As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, various policies were implemented to break the chain of spread of the Covid-19 virus in Indonesia. One of the efforts made by the government in Indonesia is by applying an appeal to the public to carry out physical distancing, namely an appeal to maintain distance between people, stay away from activities in all forms of crowds, associations, and avoid meetings that involve many people. This effort is aimed at the community so that it can be done to break the chain of spreading the Covid-19 pandemic that is currently happening.

The government implements a policy, namely Work From Home (WFH). This policy is an effort applied to the community in order to complete all work at home. Education in Indonesia has also become one of the areas affected by the covid-19 pandemic. With the existence of restrictions on interaction, the Ministry of Education in Indonesia also issued a policy, namely by dismissing schools and replacing the Teaching and Learning Activities process by using an online system. By using this online learning system, sometimes various problems faced by students and teachers arise, such as subject matter that has not been completed by the teacher and then the teacher replaces it with other assignments. This is a complaint for students because the assignments given by the teacher are more.²

Another problem with this online learning system is that access to information is constrained by signals which causes slow access to information. Students are sometimes left with information due to inadequate signals. As a result, they are late in collecting an assignment given by the teacher. Not to mention for teachers who check the many assignments that have been given to students, making gadget storage space even more limited. The application of online learning also makes educators think again about the learning models

¹ <https://bnpb.go.id/infografis/update-penanganan-covid19-di-indonesia-13-juli-2020>, Update on Covid-19 Handling in Indonesia, National Disaster Management Agency - July 13, 2020, accessed July 13, 2020

² Circular of the Minister of Education and Culture number 3 of 2020 concerning the Prevention of Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19) in the Education Institution.

and methods to be used. Initially, a teacher has prepared a learning model that will be used, then must change the learning model.³

Based on an interview with one of the teachers at Sekolah Menengah Pertama Islam Terpadu (SMPIT) Nurul Fikri Tulungagung, learning that was previously carried out face-to-face at school must also be converted into online at each home. Teachers are worried that the entry of students to school will trigger an increase in the transmission of the covid-19 virus. However, online learning must also be circumvented so that students don't feel bored while studying at home.

Teachers according to Law no.14 of 2005 are professional educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students in early childhood education through formal education, basic education, and secondary education.⁴ The success of the teacher's task in planning, organizing, mobilizing and directing all class resources in achieving goals is an indicator and the effectiveness of a teacher in managing his class, besides that the teacher's ability to build a class can also be seen when the teacher is able to create learning interactions that take place in situations and conditions that are pleasant for students. This is in line with what was conveyed by Marland (1990: 10) who said that as class managers, teachers must master the main art in their profession, namely the art of managing the class. According to him, there are three characteristics of the success of teachers in carrying out their activities, namely: (1) attentive and never giving up, (2) the explanation is easy to understand, and (3) good classroom management.⁵

Classroom Management

According to E. Mulyasa, classroom management is a teacher's skill to create a conducive learning climate and control it in case of disruption in learning. Management or often referred to as the word management which comes from English, namely "to manage" which means to organize, manage, and implement.⁶ Due to the swift flow of

³ <https://iain-surakarta.ac.id/hikmah-pandemi-covid-19-bagi-pendidikan-di-indonesia/>, Lessons from the Covid-19 Pandemic, accessed on June 10, 2020

⁴ Ahmad Tafsir, *Strategi Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan Agama Islam di Sekolah*, Bandung : Maestro, 2008

⁵ A. Tabrani Rusyan, Wiwin Winarni, Asep Hermawan, *Seri Pembaharuan Pendidikan Membangun Kelas Aktif Dan Inspiratif*, (Yogyakarta: Deepublish, 2020), 1

⁶ E. Mulyasa, *Menjadi Guru Profesional* (Bandung: Rosda Karya, 2005), 91.

additional loanwords being added to Indonesian, the English term was later Indonesianized to become "management". According to the term management is the management, implementation, management of the use of resources effectively to achieve the desired goals / objectives.⁷

Made Pidarta, quoted by Syaiful Bahri Djamarah and Aswan Zaini, said that class management is "the process of selecting and using appropriate tools for class problems and situations. This means that the teacher is in charge of creating, repairing, and maintaining a class system / organization. So that students can take advantage of it." Meanwhile, according to Sudirman N, "class management is an effort to utilize class potential. Therefore the class has a certain role and function in supporting the success of the educational interaction process. So in order to provide encouragement and stimulation for students to learn, the class must be managed properly by the teacher."⁸

The objectives of classroom management or management are essentially contained in educational goals, both in general and specifically. In general, the purpose of classroom management is to provide facilities for various student learning activities in the social, emotional and intellectual environment in the classroom. The facilities provided allow students to study and work, create a social atmosphere that provides satisfaction, an atmosphere of discipline, intellectual, emotional and attitude development, and students' appreciation.⁹

Time and Location of Research

Imam Gunawan said "the selection of research locations must be based on considerations of attractiveness, uniqueness, and suitability with the chosen topic."¹⁰ The researcher chose the research location at the Nurul Fikri Integrated Islamic Junior High School, which is located in Kedungwaru Village, Kedungwaru District, Tulungagung Regency. The selection of the research location is based on the consideration of strategic locations that are easy to reach so that it

⁷ Pius A.Partanto dan M.Dahlan al-Barry, *Kamus Ilmiah Populer* (Surabaya : Arkola, 1994), 434

⁸ Syaiful Bahri Djamarah, *Guru dan Anak Didik dalam Interaksi Edukatif*, (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2000), Cet. I, 172

⁹ Sudirman N, dkk, *Ilmu Pendidikan* (Bandung : Remadja Karya CV, 1987), 31

¹⁰ Imam Gunawan, *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif: Teori dan Praktik*, (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2013), 278

supports and facilitates the process of conducting research. The time of this research took place since the submission of the research permit, namely on July 21, 2020 to September 30, 2020.

Data collection

1. Observation

Researchers made observations related to class management and implementation of Islamic Education learning during the Covid-19 pandemic at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung online through the WhatsUp social media chat application.

2. Interview

This interview was shown to explore information about the implementation of classroom learning and management carried out by Islamic Education teachers at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung. The interview was conducted in a structured manner through a video conferencing application.

3. Documentation

The documentation obtained by researchers in conducting research at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung is: school profile data, circular on the implementation of learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, photos of the school environment, and photo interviews.

Data Analysis

The data analysis used in this research are:

1. Data reduction

Reducing data means summarizing, selecting the main things, focusing on the important things, looking for themes and patterns and removing unnecessary.¹¹ Data from online interviews with Islamic Religious Education teachers and the Principal of SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung were summarized and selected according to the subject matter.

2. Conclusion drawing

Verification is the review of field notes or the review and exchange of ideas among peers to develop an "inter-subjective agreement", or also broad attempts to place a copy of a finding in another data set.¹²

¹¹ Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2010), 338

¹² *Ibid*, ... 9

Results and Discussion

Classroom Management during The Covid-19 Pandemic

In setting students in the classroom, the researcher focuses on two points, namely how the teacher provides class assignments and provides guidance to students in the learning process during the Covid-19 pandemic. The following is an explanation from Mr. Huda as a teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung:

*"There are many types of assignments. So, for learning during this pandemic, we, including those at PAI, do not only give direct assignments, yes, but we also give explanations for the children first. So through the wa group the learning process continues, we still explain the children before we give assignments. So it's not just that we give assignments without a prefix and a prologue given to such students. Now the form of the assignment is usually a written assignment, for example in the form of a question, then later it will be done by the child and later the answer is usually sent via wa rich like that. So after the teacher explains the material in a certain chapter after that, usually to measure the child's ability, yes, we do a kind of post test or quiz with short answers and so on. "*¹³

Based on the interview above, it is known that the Islamic Religious Education teacher in giving class assignments during the Covid-19 pandemic always starts with a prologue and material explanation first. The form of the assignment is in writing in the form of questions then the child answers and sends the answer via the WhatsUp social media application. And to measure children's abilities, the Islamic Religious Education teacher also provides a kind of post test or quiz with short answers.

"Usually, we still have feedback that the students already understand or do not yet understand the content of the learning being delivered. When there are students who do not understand, they are still given the opportunity to ask questions. Now to guide it, we usually explain it again through voice notes from the WhatsUp application because if the

¹³ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 24, 2020

writing is sometimes ambiguous, so usually when there are students who don't understand, we try to clarify our explanation again by using voice messages through the WhatsUp application. So all this time our guidance is still like that. Even then, students are given references to learning content, so maybe if you don't understand, you can search the internet or we can give a summary of presentation slides and so on, that is also an effort to guide students who have learning difficulties."¹⁴

Based on the interview above, it is known that in guiding students during the Covid-19 pandemic, the Islamic Religious Education teacher held feedback to determine the extent to which students understood the learning content. Then the Islamic Religious Education teacher also provides opportunities for students who do not understand to ask questions. The teacher also explains back the material that has not been understood through voice messages so that students better understand the subject matter. Then another effort to guide students who have learning difficulties is that the teacher provides references that can be searched on the internet and provides a summary in the form of presentation slides.

Classroom Order during The Covid-19 Pandemic

In terms of class order, the researcher focused on three points, namely how the teacher provided classroom discipline, gave appreciation, and how the teacher advised / reprimanded students who were noisy in class during the Covid-19 pandemic. The following is an explanation from Mr. Huda as a teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung:

*"For classroom discipline, students are asked to fill in the attendance list at the beginning and end of the lesson. The name of the WhatsUp social media account must be the student's full name, so that the teacher can monitor student attendance during the learning process. Then there is a deadline for submitting daily assignments."*¹⁵

¹⁴ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 25, 2020

¹⁵ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 25, 2020

Based on the interview above, the rules given by the PAI teacher during the Covid-19 pandemic were asking students to fill in attendance at the beginning and at the end of the lesson. The teacher also asks students to use real names in the wa account so that the teacher can easily assess students when the learning process takes place. Then the teacher also gave a deadline in submitting assignments.

*"Gives appreciation to students who actively participate in the learning process and also rewards providing internet quota every month for those who are full in collecting assignments."*¹⁶

Based on the interview above, in giving appreciation to students during the Covid-19 pandemic, the teacher gave appreciation to students who actively participated in learning. Then the teacher also provides a reward in the form of an internet quota every month for those who are full in collecting assignments.

*"It is rare that there are students who make a lot of noise in class forums. In fact, the problem through the WhatsUp group is that sometimes students do not standby online. So usually after filling in the attendance list, only a few children are online in the WhatsUp group to take part in the lessons. Usually the others just fill out the attendance list. After that, yesterday we had an interview with his parents, some were playing games, some were opening other content and so on. So it doesn't make it rowdy but instead makes it quiet. Maybe the students are already bored. So, after almost three months of online learning, the children looked bored. So it was proven when the teacher explained that online we saw only a few children listening. Our follow-up, yes, we will ask the news, whether it is to the children themselves or their parents, and yes, because at home the main collaboration is with parents to oversee the student learning process while at home."*¹⁷

Based on the interview above, it is known that during the Covid-19 pandemic there were obstacles that there were some students who did not participate in the full online learning process. After the

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 25, 2020

teacher asked the parents of students, it turned out that there were students playing games, opening other content and so on. This may happen because students feel bored because it has been going on for three months of online learning. So the follow-up given by the Islamic Religious Education teacher is to ask directly to the student and the student's parents. Because it needs cooperation with parents to oversee the student learning process while at home.

Learning Process during The Covid-19 Pandemic

In showing creative learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, the following is an explanation from Mr. Huda as an Islamic Religious Education teacher at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung:

*"And creativity will also be limited. For example, if the Thoharoh practice material is practiced, maybe if it is done face-to-face, students can immediately practice how to do tayamum correctly. So during the pandemic, the practice of Tayamum was conveyed online with video tutorials on the correct method of Tayamum. Then students practice tayamum by sending videos to the teacher. So it is true that online creativity is also rather limited."*¹⁸

Based on the interview above, how the teacher showed creative learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, which was limited in material that required practice. Because the teacher cannot give an example directly to students but only provides tutorials via video online.

Adjustment of Methods to Learning Content during The Covid-19 Pandemic

In adjusting the learning content during the Covid-19 pandemic, the following is an explanation from Mr. Huda as an Islamic Religious Education teacher at SMPIT Nurul Fikri Tulungagung:

"Because the learning is done fully online, we have a little trouble adjusting from normal conditions. The explanation of the material, which is usually done in a lecture, is interrupted when it is delivered via

¹⁸ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 26, 2020

*WhatsUp voice notes. Sometimes students take a long time to respond so that the question and answer process in learning is interrupted. But basically, students still respond even though it's a bit long"*¹⁹

Based on the interview above in organizing or adjusting learning content during the Covid-19 pandemic, the teacher used the lecture method via voice messages and questions and answers via the WhatsUp application. Because the teacher hopes there are two directions, namely not only presenting the material but also asking questions to be answered by students.

Conclusion

The role of Islamic Religious Education teachers in effective classroom management during the Covid-19 pandemic at SMPIT Nurul Fikri experienced many obstacles, namely not being familiar with online learning models. Because during normal conditions (before the Covid-19 pandemic), online learning models were rarely used. Teachers have difficulty delivering learning content because they are not used to learning online. There is no software to support the online learning process. The teacher only uses social media applications. The reason for using social media is its ease of use. All parents of students must have social media. So it can be said that the entire learning process is carried out through social media. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the content of learning was no different from normal conditions. The learning content that is delivered still refers to the National Education Curriculum. Assignments to students refer to the Student Worksheets provided by the school before the Covid-19 pandemic. Students work on assignments based on Student Worksheets, then send the results to the teacher via social media.

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¹⁹ Interview with Mr. Nurul Syamsi Bil Huda as Teacher of Islamic Religious Education at SMPIT Nurul Fikri, on September 29, 2020

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